

Towards an OSF-based Registered Report Template for Software Engineering Controlled Experiments

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Context: The empirical software engineering community has advanced experimentation practices, yet controlled experiments are still reported with insufficient rigor, affecting transparency and reproducibility. Registered Reports (RRs), which preregister hypotheses, methods and analyses before data collection, have been proposed to mitigate issues such as p-hacking, publication bias and unplanned *post hoc* analyses. *Objective:* This paper presents early results toward an RR template for Software Engineering controlled experiments using the Open Science Framework. We examine how current OSF RR types align with SE experimentation guidelines and identify gaps to be addressed in a future comprehensive template. *Method:* We analyzed selected OSF RR types in relation to established documentation guidelines for controlled experiments. *Results:* One RR type showed substantial alignment with several guideline elements, but no OSF template provides complete coverage. We also identified limitations in OSF's support for customizing RR structures. *Conclusion:* Although RRs offer a promising path to more rigorous and reproducible experimentation, existing OSF RR types do not fully meet SE requirements. Developing SE-specific RR guidelines is therefore essential.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Software engineering (SE) research still faces numerous challenges, one of which consists of obtaining and managing research artifacts [OliveiraJr et al. 2024]. Rigorous research is mainly based on transparency, credibility, and reproducibility, which are pillars in constructing and evaluating robust theories for the area's evolution [OliveiraJr et al. 2021]. Open Science principles and practices can provide a solid foundation for achieving these goals¹ [Mendez et al. 2020].

In recent years, several major SE conferences, such as ICSE² and FSE³, have introduced Artifact Tracks. These tracks focus on evaluating and promoting the quality and availability of research artifacts, such as software tools, data, and frameworks that support the reproducibility and validity of research findings. The conferences share common goals and inclusion criteria: artifacts must be functional, reusable, and publicly available in persistent repositories with proper

¹<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949>

²<https://conf.researchr.org/track/icse-2025/icse-2025-artifact-evaluation>

³<https://conf.researchr.org/track/fse-2025/fse-2025-artifacts>

documentation. By incorporating these tracks, the conferences highlight the importance of artifacts in ensuring the transparency, reliability, and reproducibility of empirical studies in software engineering.

To emphasize artifact quality, many conferences, including ICSE and FSE, collaborate with the ACM's badging system. This system awards badges to artifacts that meet specific criteria, such as functionality and reusability. These badges recognize high-quality artifacts that particularly enhance the reproducibility and reusability of research. Additionally, the ACM badges encourage the community to prioritize transparency and the open sharing of research results, ensuring that artifacts are accessible and valuable for researchers seeking to replicate or build upon existing findings.

Although reproducibility and reliability are crucial, many Software Engineering studies still face challenges, including issues with replicability, biases in results, and incomplete research artifacts.

In response to these challenges, Registered Reports (RRs) have emerged as a promising solution, as they enhance research quality by requiring hypotheses and study protocols to be established prior to data collection, thereby reducing bias and increasing transparency. RRs are peer-reviewed, which straightforwardly improves such characteristics. RRs are being adopted at several SE conferences, including ICSE, ESEM⁴, ICSME⁵, and MSR⁶.

Recent studies have addressed this topic, including that of Ernst and Baldassarre [2023]. However, this topic remains crucial for the reproducibility, reliability, and transparency of empirical studies.

In this paper, we focus on the following research question: **“how can we design an RR template for SE controlled experiments based on existing guidelines?”**. To do so, we propose and discuss an initial template based on the Open Science Framework (OSF) platform. OSF offers various RR templates for different kinds of empirical studies. Therefore, we analyzed and compared all of them to determine how well they align with the specific guidelines for SE-controlled experiments compiled by Jedlitschka et al. [2008]. We also discuss the limitations of this study, share the lessons learned, and suggest potential future actions.

Rather than delivering a complete template, this paper provides a structured analysis that lays the methodological foundations for developing such a template in future work.

Although several SE venues already offer RR tracks, their templates are typically not publicly standardized or are derived from OSF structures. Because our focus is to analyze the foundational RR types provided by OSF, which act as cross-disciplinary baselines, we deliberately limited our scope to OSF templates. Future work will map the templates used in ICSE, ESEM, ICSME, and MSR to complement the present analysis.

2 GUIDELINES FOR DOCUMENTING CONTROLLED EXPERIMENTS AND RR IN SE

Jedlitschka et al. [2008] present a set of guidelines for experiments in SE. These guidelines provide detailed guidance on the expected content of sections and subsections for reporting controlled experiments and *quasi*-experiments. The guidelines are organized into sections, each one focusing on a core component of controlled experiment reporting in SE. These sections cover structured abstract, introduction, experiment planning, execution, analysis, interpretation, and conclusions. Table 1 summarizes these guidelines by section and scope.

The first element emphasizes the importance of a clear, informative title (**G1**) that explicitly states that the work is a controlled experiment, as well as complete authorship details (**G2**), including contact information for accountability and follow-up. The structured abstract (**G3–G8**) plays a central role, as it must present the background and motivation of the study (**G3**), define its objectives and research questions (**G4**), describe the statistical context and methods employed

⁴<https://conf.researchr.org/track/esem-2025/esem-2025-technical-track>

⁵<https://conf.researchr.org/home/icsme-2025>

⁶<https://2025.msrfconf.org/>

Table 1. Experiment Guidelines by Jedlitschka et al. [2008]

ID	Section	Sub-Section	Scope
G1	Title		<title>+ ". A controlled experiment"
G2	Authorship		Does it include contact information?
G3	Structured Abstract	Background	Why is this research important?
G4	Structured Abstract	Objective	What is the question addressed with this research?
G5	Structured Abstract	Methods	What is the statistical context and methods applied?
G6	Structured Abstract	Results	What are the main findings? Practical implications?
G7	Structured Abstract	Limitations	What are the weaknesses of this research?
G8	Structured Abstract	Conclusions	What is the conclusion?
G9	Keywords		Areas of research, treatments, dependent variables, and study type
G10	Introduction	Problem Statement	What is the problem? Where does it occur? Who has observed it? Why is it important?
G11	Introduction	Research Objectives	Analyze <Object(s) of study>-for the purpose of <purpose>
G12	Introduction	Context	What are the environmental factors that impact generalizability?
G13	Related Work		How does it relate to existing research or state of the practice?
G14	Experiment Planning	Goals	Formalization of goals, defining important constructs
G15	Experiment Planning	Experimental Units	From which population will the sample be drawn?
G16	Experiment Planning	Experimental Material	Which objects are selected and why?
G17	Experiment Planning	Tasks	Which tasks have to be performed by the subjects?
G18	Experiment Planning	Hypotheses, Variables	Formalization of hypotheses and variables
G19	Experiment Planning	Design	What type of experimental design was chosen?
G20	Experiment Planning	Procedure	How will the experiment (data collection) be performed?
G21	Experiment Planning	Analysis Procedure	How will the data be analyzed?
G22	Execution		Main purpose: describe any deviations from the plan
G23	Execution	Preparation	What was done to prepare for the execution of the experiment?
G24	Execution	Deviations	Describe any deviations from the plan, e.g., data collection
G25	Analysis	Descriptive Statistics	What are the results from descriptive statistics?
G26	Analysis	Data Set Reduction	Was it necessary to reduce the dataset? Why and how?
G27	Analysis	Hypothesis Testing	How was the data evaluated? Was the model validated?
G28	Interpretation	Evaluation of Results	Explain the results in relation to earlier research
G29	Interpretation	Threats to Validity	How is the validity of the results assured? Discuss potential biases
G30	Interpretation	Inferences	Inferences drawn from the data to more general conditions
G31	Interpretation	Lessons Learned	What was learned during the experiment?
G32	Conclusions	Summary	Provide a concise summary of the research and results
G33	Conclusions	Impact	Description of impacts on cost, schedule, and quality
G34	Conclusions	Future Work	What other experiments could be run to further investigate the findings?
G35	Acknowledgements		Acknowledge sponsors, participants, and contributors
G36	References		All cited literature must be presented in the requested format
G37	Appendices		Material, raw data, detailed analyses for reproducibility

(G5), summarize the main results and their practical implications (G6), acknowledge the study's limitations (G7), and provide a clear conclusion (G8). This standardized format makes it easier for readers and reviewers to understand, compare, and reuse the reported evidence.

Keywords (G9) must be carefully chosen to reflect the domain, treatments, dependent variables, and study type, supporting efficient indexing in scientific databases. In the introduction (G10–G12), researchers should present a well-defined problem statement (G10), explain the research objectives (G11), and clarify the context in which the study arises, including environmental and organizational factors that may affect generalizability (G12). The introduction should also be complemented by a discussion of related work (G13), which situates the experiment within prior studies and identifies its novelty or added contribution.

The experiment planning section (G14–G21) provides the foundation for methodological rigor. Goals must be formalized (G14), while the description of experimental units (G15), materials (G16), and tasks (G17) clarifies the scope of the study. Hypotheses and variables should be explicitly defined (G18), and the chosen experimental design

explained (G19). Furthermore, the procedures for execution and data collection (G20) and the analysis procedure (G21) should be described in sufficient detail to enable replication and critical evaluation.

Execution (G22–G24) is then reported with emphasis on preparation activities (G23) and transparent documentation of any deviations from the original plan (G24). This is followed by the analysis section (G25–G27), where descriptive statistics (G25) provide an overview of the data (dataset reduction) is justified if applied (G26), and hypothesis testing (G27), which is performed for validating or rejecting the proposed assumptions. The interpretation of results (G28–G31) links findings to earlier research (G28), discusses threats to validity and potential biases (G29), and formulates inferences that extend to broader contexts (G30). Lessons learned (G31) are also emphasized, capturing insights gained during the study.

Finally, the conclusions (G32–G34) must concisely summarize the research and results (G32), highlight their impact on aspects such as cost, schedule, and quality (G33), and suggest directions for future work (G34). The closing elements of acknowledgments (G35), references (G36), and appendices (G37) strengthen the credibility and reproducibility of the study by recognizing contributions, providing properly formatted citations, and sharing supplementary material, raw data, and detailed analyses.

3 REGISTERED REPORTS (RR) IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING AND THE OSF FRAMEWORK

This section presents essential concepts on RR and the OSF framework.

3.1 Registered Reports

Science must be transparent and accessible, regardless of study results. Despite its theoretical and empirical value, researchers often lack the motivation to conduct replications or report negative results [Crawford and Stucki 1990; Nosek and Lakens 2014]. Access to the work of other researchers is necessary for evaluating, replicating, and advancing knowledge [Crawford and Stucki 1990].

The traditional scientific process involves sharing research methods and findings mainly through journal articles, theses, and dissertations. However, many software engineering research artifacts are not shared in a way that allows them to be reproduced [Ernst and Baldassarre 2023]. To address this issue, it may be helpful to preregister a study protocol, a practice successfully employed in fields such as medicine for decades. Preregistration, also known as a Registered Report (RR), involves openly sharing the study protocol and discussing its validity [Silva et al. 2017].

RRs are scientific publications that precede the publication process. They include a detailed research protocol, research questions, a literature review, and specifications for the data analysis procedures to be used. This practice has recently become present in some computer science conferences and journals [Ernst and Baldassarre 2023].

RRs have two stages: Stage 1, where the protocol is registered and formalized, and Stage 2, which reports the execution of the study in accordance with the protocol. Any deviations or changes must be reported (in general, we expect deviations to be minimal).

An RR is a valuable tool to ensure a certain level of quality in study design. For example, it ensures that the hypotheses of a confirmatory study are predefined rather than being defined after analyzing the data to fit the results. Researchers define their research questions, the reasons for pursuing the research, and exactly how they will try to answer their questions [Mendez et al. 2020].

An RR is based on the philosophy that it is essential to focus on research planning and to evaluate the results without bias, to minimize distortions in scientific findings [Chambers and Tzavella 2022]. This method involves initiating the evaluation before any data is collected, enabling early feedback that can save time and effort. Seeking opinions from

individuals outside of the research group can avoid potential issues with research practices and provide valuable early feedback to researchers [Ernst and Baldassarre 2023].

The process of preparing an RR involves two stages [Chambers 2019]. In the first stage, authors submit their research questions, theory, detailed methods, analysis plans, and any preliminary data as required. After a thorough analysis and review based on specific criteria, proposals that are favorably evaluated receive a conditional acceptance, which means that the venue (journal or conference) commits to publishing the final article regardless of whether the hypotheses are supported, as long as the authors adhere to their approved protocols and interpret the results based on the evidence. The approved protocol, results, and discussion are included in the second stage.

The advantages of RRs include shareable protocols for research replication, a focus on research rather than publication, and greater rigor in reporting. However, this practice may also have disadvantages, such as requiring greater effort from researchers, currently facing limited acceptance by journals, and not applying to all research strategies [Ernst and Baldassarre 2023]. Multiple RRs for various areas are accessible on the PCI Registered Reports Community⁷ website. An example of an RR for a SE controlled experiment can be found at <https://rr.peercommunityin.org/articles/rec?id=746>.

3.2 The Open Science Framework (OSF)

The Open Science Framework⁸ (OSF) platform is designed to assist researchers, whether they are working on collaborative projects or not. This platform connects data, pre-publications, and research project progress, offering opportunities for publishing, categorizing, and obtaining community feedback. It has the following main features:

- The functionality dedicated to **Institutions** is designed for universities and research institutes, aiming to foster a community among researchers. It simplifies the management of research projects by providing features to organize, document, and securely share research materials and data;
- The **Meetings** feature streamlines the process of sharing posters and presentations openly at academic conferences. Conference organizers can create a dedicated page on OSF for participants to submit their work;
- **Preprints** on the OSF platform are an effective and agile way for researchers to share their preliminary results with the academic community before submitting them for peer review in scientific journals; and
- The **Registries** feature provides a centralized and accessible platform for academic community members to share and explore studies conducted by others. It enables the investigation of overviews, metadata, files, resources, components, links, analytics, and comments.

An exemplary general OSF-based RR can be found at <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/JSZNK>. The resulting publication of this RR is available at <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/cdgyh>.

4 AN OSF-BASED RR TEMPLATE PROPOSAL

In this section, we demonstrate how we developed an RR Stage-1 template for Software Engineering controlled experiments based on the OSF RR types and documentation items.

We started by analyzing and comparing each RR type with each other (Section 4.1). We familiarized ourselves with the RR types available in the OSF platform and their purpose. Subsequently, we excluded RR types that were unsuitable for controlled experiments. In the final stage (Section 4.2), we compared the recommendations Jedlitschka et al. [2008]

⁷<https://rr.peercommunityin.org/>

⁸<https://osf.io/>

with each remaining OSF RR type. We will analyze and discuss the lessons learned and the limitations of the template proposal in Section 4.3.

4.1 The OSF Registered Report Types

The OSF platform offers 11 types of RRs to formalize and enhance transparency in scientific research, as shown below. Every kind of RR possesses distinct characteristics that cater to various research needs.

The **OSF Preregistration** (RR.1) type is suitable for providing a detailed, transparent narrative of a study from initial planning to final results.

The **Open-Ended Registration** (RR.2) consists of a summary narrative of the study information, allowing the inclusion of supplementary files or additional information.

Qualitative Preregistration (RR.3) is intended to guide qualitative research studies by providing detailed information about objectives, design, data collection, and analysis.

Secondary Data Preregistration (RR.4) is crucial for conducting analyses based on existing data, as it provides information on research questions, data description, variables, and planned statistical analyses.

The **Generalized Systematic Review Registration** (RR.5) is intended for preregistration of systematic reviews, providing information on methods, search strategies, screening, data extraction, and synthesis.

The **Registered Report Protocol Preregistration** (RR.6) Pre-registration type is required for studies that have received in-principle acceptance from journals offering Registered Reports.

The **OSF-Standard Pre-Data Collection Registration** (RR.7) is crucial for providing information on the status of data collection and data access.

Preregistration Template from AsPredicted.org (RR.8) is intended to ensure a complete description of the study, covering aspects such as questions/hypotheses, variables, statistical analyses, and other relevant details.

The **Replication Recipe (Brandt et al., 2013): Post-Completion** (RR.9) provides a framework for detailed recording of planned methodological procedures, ensuring transparency and reproducibility in replication.

The **Replication Recipe (Brandt et al., 2013): Pre-Registration** (RR.10) is designed to register replication attempts of pre-existing studies, providing details about the objectives, methods, and planned analyses.

Preregistration in Social Psychology (RR.11) is explicitly intended for the pre-registration of studies in Social Psychology, covering aspects such as hypotheses, variables, methods, analyses, and other relevant details.

Table 2 summarizes the documentation items for RR.1, RR.3, RR.10, and RR.11 OSF Registered Report Types. The complete table, which includes all 11 RR types, is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11114264>. We excluded the types RR.2, RR.4, RR.5, RR.6, RR.7, RR.8, and RR.9 because they are unsuitable for controlled experiments.

The “Metadata” category is common to all 11 RR types. Certain identical items are under different categories, such as “Exclusion Criteria” under “Analysis and Replication Evaluation” for RR.10 and “Methods” for RR.11.

RR.1 and RR.3 are the types of RR that have the most additional items (Category) compared to the other types. The main distinction between these two types is that RR.3 is used for qualitative research studies, while RR.1 concerns a more general study.

4.2 Mapping Experimentation Guidelines to OSF Registered Reports Types

This subsection presents how the documentation guidelines for controlled experiments [Jedlitschka et al. 2008] map onto the selected OSF Registered Report (RR) types. We first summarize the overall coverage based on the comparative tables

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Table 2. Documentation Items of RR.1, RR.3, RR.10, and RR.11 OSF Registered Report Types

Category	Item	RR.1	RR.3	RR.10	RR.11
Metadata	Title	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Description	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Contributors	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Category	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Licensing	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Subjects	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Tags	✓	✓	✓	✓
Study Information	Specific, Concise, and Testable Hypotheses	✓			
Study Information	Research Aims		✓		
Study Information	Type of Aim		✓		
Study Information	Research question(s)		✓		
Study Information	Anticipated Duration		✓		
Design Plan	Study Type	✓			
Design Plan	Blinding Type	✓			
Design Plan	Factors and Treatments	✓			
Design Plan	Randomization	✓			
Design Plan	Study Design		✓		
Design Plan	Sampling and Case Selection Strategy		✓		
Data Collection	Data Source(s) and Data Type(s)		✓		
Data Collection	Data Collection Methods		✓		
Data Collection	Data Collection Tools, Instruments or Plans		✓		
Data Collection	Stopping Criteria		✓		
Sampling Plan	Existing Data Use	✓			
Sampling Plan	Explanation of Existing Data	✓			
Sampling Plan	Data Collection Procedures	✓			
Sampling Plan	Sample Size and Rationale	✓			
Sampling Plan	Stopping Rule	✓			
Variables	Manipulated Variables	✓			
Variables	Measurable Variables	✓			
Variables	Combination of Variables in Index	✓			
Analysis Plan	Statistical Models	✓			
Analysis Plan	Data Transformation, Centering, and Recoding		✓		✓
Analysis Plan	Coding Scheme for Categorical Variables	✓			
Analysis Plan	Inference Criteria	✓			
Analysis Plan	Data Exclusion	✓			✓
Analysis Plan	Missing Data	✓			
Analysis Plan	Exploratory Analysis	✓			
Analysis Plan	Approach		✓		
Analysis Plan	Process		✓		
Analysis Plan	Credibility Strategies		✓		
Analysis Plan	Reliability and Robustness Testing				✓
Analysis Plan	Revariables				✓
Analysis Plan	Statistical Technique				✓
Analysis Plan	Variable Roles				✓
Analysis Plan	Covariate Rationale				✓
Analysis Plan	Other Techniques				✓
Analysis Plan	Method of Correction				✓
Analysis Plan	Assumptions of Analysis				✓
Analysis Plan	Data Collection				✓
Analysis Plan	Data Observation				✓
Analysis Plan	Start and End Dates				✓
Analysis Plan	Additional Comments				✓
The Nature of the Effect	Description		✓		
The Nature of the Effect	Replication Importance			✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Effect Size			✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Confidence Interval			✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Sample Size			✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Original Study Conducted			✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Replication Confidence			✓	

included in this subsection, followed by a detailed examination of RR.3, the OSF RR type with the highest guideline coverage. A discussion of uncovered guidelines and their implications concludes the subsection.

Table 3 shows how the experiment guidelines map to the OSF RR types, considering which guidelines are satisfied for each RR type.

Table 4 presents a different perspective of Table 3 by summarizing the comparison of RR types from the viewpoint of each guideline, that is, indicating for each guideline which RR types satisfy it.

Overall Mapping Overview. Tables 3 and 4 show that coverage across RR types varies substantially. RR.3 maps 33 out of 37 guidelines, followed by RR.1 with 31. This broader coverage in RR.3 is largely due to its comprehensive structure for qualitative research, which incidentally aligns with several documentation and planning requirements of controlled experiments. Given this level of adherence, we now analyze RR.3 in more depth to understand how its categories relate to the specific guidelines and where gaps remain.

RR.3 Categories and Their Alignment with Guidelines. RR.3 is organized into six major categories: Metadata, Study Information, Design Plan, Data Collection, Analysis Plan and Miscellaneous. Each category corresponds to multiple documentation and planning requirements of controlled experiments.

Table 3. Types of OSF Registered Reports and Respective Controlled Experimentation Guidelines

OSF RR Type	Controlled Experimentation Guidelines				Count
	Doc.	Planning	Operation	Analysis	
RR.1	G.1, G.2, G.3, G.4, G.5, G.6, G.10, G.11, G.12, G.13, G.36, G.37	G.14, G.15, G.16, G.17, G.18, G.19, G.20, G.21	G.23, G.24	G.25, G.26, G.27, G.28, G.29, G.30, G.32, G.33, G.34	31
RR.2	G.1, G.2, G.13	G.15	G.23, G.24		6
RR.3	G.1, G.2, G.3, G.4, G.5, G.6, G.7, G.8, G.9, G.10, G.11, G.12	G.14, G.15, G.16, G.17, G.18, G.19, G.20, G.21	G.22, G.23, G.24	G.25, G.26, G.27, G.28, G.29, G.30, G.31, G.32, G.33, G.34	33
RR.4	G.1, G.2, G.4, G.5, G.11, G.13	G.14, G.15, G.16, G.17, G.18, G.19, G.20, G.21	G.22, G.23	G.25, G.26, G.27, G.28, G.29	21
RR.5	G.1, G.2, G.3, G.10, G.13, G.37				6
RR.6	G.1, G.2, G.35, G.36, G.37		G.23, G.24		7
RR.7	G.1, G.2, G.36, G.37		G.24		5
RR.8	G.1, G.2, G.3, G.4, G.5, G.7, G.10, G.37	G.14, G.15, G.18, G.19, G.20, G.21	G.22, G.23, G.24	G.26, G.27, G.29, G.30	21
RR.9	G.1, G.2, G.4, G.5, G.6, G.7, G.8, G.37	G.14, G.15, G.16, G.18, G.20, G.21			15
RR.10	G.1, G.2, G.3, G.4, G.5, G.6, G.7, G.8, G.10, G.11, G.12, G.37	G.14, G.15, G.16, G.17, G.18, G.19, G.20, G.21	G.23, G.24	G.27, G.28, G.29	25
RR.11	G.1, G.2, G.3, G.4, G.5, G.6, G.8, G.10, G.11, G.12, G.37	G.14, G.15, G.16, G.17, G.18, G.19, G.20, G.21	G.23, G.24	G.25, G.26, G.27, G.28, G.29, G.30, G.32, G.34	29

Table 4. Experimentation Guidelines per OSF Registered Reports Types

Experiment Guidelines		Types of OSF Registered Reports											Count
stage	ID	RR.1	RR.2	RR.3	RR.4	RR.5	RR.6	RR.7	RR.8	RR.9	RR.10	RR.11	
Documentation	G.1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	11
Documentation	G.2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	11
Documentation	G.3	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	6
Documentation	G.4	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	7
Documentation	G.5	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	7
Documentation	G.6	✓		✓					✓	✓	✓	✓	5
Documentation	G.7			✓					✓	✓	✓	✓	4
Documentation	G.8			✓						✓	✓	✓	4
Documentation	G.9			✓									1
Documentation	G.10	✓		✓		✓			✓		✓	✓	6
Documentation	G.11	✓		✓	✓						✓	✓	5
Documentation	G.12	✓		✓							✓	✓	4
Documentation	G.13	✓	✓		✓	✓							4
Planning	G.14	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	7
Planning	G.15	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	8
Planning	G.16	✓		✓	✓					✓	✓	✓	6
Planning	G.17	✓		✓	✓					✓	✓	✓	5
Planning	G.18	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	7
Planning	G.19	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	6
Planning	G.20	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	7
Planning	G.21	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	7
Operation	G.22			✓	✓				✓				3
Operation	G.23	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓		✓	✓	8
Operation	G.24	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	9
Analysis	G.25	✓		✓	✓							✓	4
Analysis	G.26	✓		✓	✓				✓			✓	5
Analysis	G.27	✓		✓	✓				✓		✓	✓	6
Analysis	G.28	✓		✓	✓						✓	✓	5
Analysis	G.29	✓		✓	✓						✓	✓	6
Analysis	G.30	✓		✓					✓			✓	4
Analysis	G.31			✓									1
Analysis	G.32	✓		✓								✓	3
Analysis	G.33	✓		✓									2
Analysis	G.34	✓		✓								✓	3
Documentation	G.35						✓						1
Documentation	G.36	✓					✓	✓					3
Documentation	G.37	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	8
Count		31	6	33	21	6	7	5	21	15	25	29	—

Metadata. This category aligns with guidelines G1 and G2 (title and authorship), G9 (keywords), and parts of G3 and G4 because the description often summarizes background and objectives. These elements correspond to the fundamental descriptive requirements of controlled experiment reporting.

Study Information. This category aligns with G10 (problem definition), G11 (research objectives) and G12 (context). RR.3 explicitly requires a clear statement of aims and research questions, which supports the early formalization of the rationale behind the study.

Design Plan. The Design Plan corresponds to G14 through G21. RR.3 requires authors to specify the type of study, the sampling strategy and the rationale for case selection. Although originally intended for qualitative research, these fields help formalize constructs, identify experimental units, describe procedures and outline intended analyses, all of which are central to controlled experiment planning.

Data Collection. This category aligns with G16 and G17 (materials and tasks), G20 (data collection procedures) and G24 (recording deviations). RR.3 requires detailed descriptions of sources, tools, instruments and methods, mirroring expectations for controlled experiments in Software Engineering.

Analysis Plan. This category reflects guidelines G21 (analysis procedure) and G25 through G30 (descriptive statistics, inferential testing, interpretation and inferences). RR.3 includes a strong emphasis on analytic transparency and credibility strategies, which complements SE controlled experiment documentation even though it was not designed specifically for this purpose.

Miscellaneous. This category loosely aligns with G31 because it includes optional reflections about the researcher's position and assumptions. These reflections support transparency and may help interpret replication efforts, although the alignment is indirect.

Missing Categories and Uncovered Guidelines. Even though RR.3 covers most documentation and planning guidelines, two essential guideline groups are not addressed. The first group is the Sampling Plan, which includes G22, G23 and G24. RR.3 does not explicitly require a justification for sample size, nor does it require reporting sampling assumptions or stopping rules. These elements are essential for statistical validity in controlled experiments and therefore should be added manually by researchers when using RR.3. The second group concerns the Nature of the Effect. Several guidelines related to effect characterization are not represented, including effect size definitions, confidence intervals, replication justification and related elements. These omissions prevent RR.3 from providing a complete preregistration structure for confirmatory experimental studies involving quantitative effect estimation. These gaps should be explicitly acknowledged when RR.3 is used as the basis for documenting Software Engineering controlled experiments. Supplementing RR.3 with additional fields that address sampling and effect modeling is recommended in order to meet the completeness expected in SE experimentation guidelines.

Implications for SE Controlled Experiment Preregistration. The uncovered guidelines have direct effects on the completeness of preregistration. RR.3 alone cannot guarantee adherence to the expectations of controlled experiment documentation in Software Engineering. The absence of sampling and effect modeling fields reduces its suitability for confirmatory quantitative studies. This reinforces the need for a hybrid or customized RR structure adapted specifically to SE, which the current OSF platform does not yet support. The mapping results indicate the importance of developing an SE specific RR template that integrates statistical planning, sampling justification and effect characterization. This

template would provide a more comprehensive preregistration structure and bring practices in Software Engineering closer to disciplines in which registered studies are more mature, such as Medicine and Psychology.

4.3 Lessons Learned and Limitations

The concept of removing obstacles to the reproducibility and transparency of research findings and artifacts is particularly challenging in the field of computer science, especially in software engineering. Therefore, we recognize that investigating RRs is a way to make these practices achievable.

Despite RR being a concept still underutilized in software engineering, we have learned that it ensures that research data are not the sole focus of a study. Instead, it emphasizes the study's design, particularly before the survey is carried out. This change of focus helps to mitigate several common threats to validity in empirical studies, such as selective reporting, data dredging, and post hoc hypothesis formulation. In other words, the process promotes a culture of planning and transparency rather than relying solely on the persuasiveness of results.

Another important lesson is that Registered Reports foster accountability and dialogue with the research community from the earliest stages of the research process. When effectively implemented, stage 1 review encourages authors to justify methodological choices, define measurable variables, and provide a clear rationale for hypotheses in advance. This also creates opportunities for reviewers to provide constructive feedback before resources are spent, ultimately improving study quality.

Nevertheless, we also observed that Registered Reports do not guarantee reproducibility or replicability. They are best suited for hypothesis-driven studies, where experimental protocols and statistical analysis plans can be pre-registered. In exploratory or design-oriented studies, which are common in software engineering, the RR format can be less directly applicable. In such cases, adaptations or complementary practices such as structured metadata and artifact sharing are necessary.

The main limitations can be summarized as follows:

Lack of protocol transparency: It is essential to ensure that readers and reviewers can verify whether the approved protocol was strictly followed. However, some major journals do not require RRs for the initial stage of a study due to time constraints. This creates a risk of partial adherence to protocols and reduces trust in the RR process, particularly in short-term or fast-paced research projects.

Lack of standardization: RRs are often written inconsistently, with missing details or without explicit hypotheses. There is still no widely adopted standard template for RR writing in software engineering, which leads to heterogeneity and difficulties in automating or streamlining the process. A metadata-driven approach and integration with open science tools could help to standardize RR content and ensure completeness.

Delay and bureaucracy in stage 1: The review of protocols in stage 1 may take several months, delaying the start of the actual study. For researchers constrained by funding cycles, academic deadlines, or short project durations, this is a significant obstacle. In addition, the need for ethics committee approval, particularly in studies involving human participants, can further extend the timeline, sometimes making RRs infeasible.

Limited coverage of research types: RRs are well aligned with confirmatory, quantitative studies, but they are less naturally suited to qualitative, exploratory, or mixed-methods approaches. This restricts their applicability in many areas of software engineering, which often rely on case studies, grounded theory, or design science research.

In relation to OSF, it provides different RR types, which present an opportunity for detailed and transparent study conception documentation, as it plans to conduct final results checking. We learned that the RR types we chose for this study are quite adequate for data-driven studies, where data are collected through measurable variables and

testable hypotheses are formulated using statistical techniques. Therefore, for the guidelines by Jedlitschka et al. [2008], we observed that most of them are considered in the analyzed RR types. However, we understand that combining RR.1 and RR.3 would be necessary to address the experiment guidelines fully. Unfortunately, OSF does not allow this customization.

Another limitation is the absence of a dedicated RR type on the OSF platform specifically focused on Software Engineering, particularly considering its research artifact types, as discussed by Oliveira Jr et al. [2024]. For instance, code repositories, UML diagrams, models, or scripts, which are central to reproducibility in SE, are not explicitly supported in the current RR templates.

Furthermore, none of the existing OSF RR types fully meet all the guidelines outlined by Jedlitschka et al. [2008]. As a result, we recommend proposing a customization or the development of new RR types in collaboration with OSF. This would enable closer alignment with SE-specific experimentation practices, improve artifact documentation, and reduce gaps between methodological planning and artifact reproducibility.

We did not apply the templates to a concrete controlled experiment due to space constraints and because the aim of this paper is methodological groundwork. A complete worked example will be included in a follow-up study.

In summary, we learned that RRs contribute positively to research integrity and planning but face significant challenges regarding adoption, standardization, and adaptation to the specific needs of software engineering. Their future success in this field will depend on broader community engagement, support for tools, and closer alignment with the diverse methodological approaches used in SE research.

Overall, the lessons learned show that RRs enhance transparency, accountability, and methodological rigor. At the same time, the limitations highlight the practical, organizational, and disciplinary barriers that must be addressed for their effective implementation. This dual perspective highlights the importance of integrating methodological innovation with infrastructural and cultural changes to make RRs fully effective in software engineering.

5 PROSPECTIVE ACTIONS

We provide a set of future actions to be taken in light of this work, with the overarching goal of enhancing the maturity, adoption, and usability of RRs for controlled experimentation in Software Engineering. These actions are not isolated; instead, they form a roadmap that bridges methodological rigor, community acceptance, and tool-supported reproducibility.

The actions listed here are intentionally prospective: they outline the next steps for advancing RR adoption in SE, rather than contributions executed within this paper.

The first step is to **review the RR types** based on the guidelines by Jedlitschka et al. [2008] and incorporate items to fill relevant missing elements. This will enhance and improve RR experiment documentation by ensuring that crucial aspects, such as context, threats to validity, and reproducibility requirements, are not overlooked. The review process will also help us distinguish between mandatory and optional elements, clarifying which parts of the RR structure should be emphasized for controlled experimentation in Software Engineering.

Another critical action is to **identify which RR elements are required, or at least suggested, by journals and conferences** that accept RR submissions. This mapping exercise will serve as a bridge between our proposed structure and the actual publication requirements. It will also serve as a valuable resource for the community, offering examples of how each RR item is written in practice. By analyzing differences across venues, we can better guide researchers on tailoring their submissions without sacrificing methodological transparency.

We will also **inquire with OSF about the option to customize the existing Registered Reports or to create a new one**. Having a dedicated template or customized workflow within OSF could significantly speed up the process of writing controlled experiment RRs. If such customization is feasible, we will seek to incorporate RR elements across a range of software engineering artifacts, including code repositories, diagrams, scripts, and domain-specific languages. Additionally, we will provide explicit guidance on how to reuse or reproduce these artifacts, thereby strengthening the reproducibility chain across experiments.

We foresee the need to **identify existing RR standards or patterns** for controlled experimentation in established fields such as Medicine and Psychology. These disciplines have a longer tradition of registered studies and could provide ready-made structures or best practices that can be adapted to the context of Software Engineering. By leveraging domain expertise from these fields, we aim to avoid reinventing the wheel and instead build upon proven strategies to formalize and accelerate RR writing in our community.

The **creation of RR metadata for interchange** among tools and environments is another prospective action. At present, there is no unified, automated solution for representing and exchanging RR data. Developing a standard metadata schema would facilitate the integration of RRs across different platforms, including repositories, submission systems, and experiment management tools. Such metadata would also support automated validation, indexing, and long-term preservation, in line with open science principles.

To standardize the RR description language and structure for experiments, we will **examine the compatibility of existing software engineering-related RRs**. This comparative analysis will highlight overlaps, gaps, and inconsistencies, helping us refine our own template. Moreover, **analyzing existing Data Management Plans (DMPs)** will provide insights into how data generated or reused in experiments should be curated, preserved, and documented. Since DMPs focus on data life cycle management and provenance, they are highly complementary to RRs. In addition, considering categories and elements of research software [Felderer et al. 2025] may further enrich RR descriptions by clarifying how software artifacts are documented, cited, and reused.

Another important line of action is to **analyze the human-related aspects required by ethical committees**. Controlled experiments in Software Engineering often involve participants such as students, professionals, or volunteers. By explicitly considering ethical requirements, particularly when sensitive data are collected or when procedures may include embarrassment, stress, or other potentially traumatic experiences, we can improve the robustness of RR descriptions and ensure compliance with institutional review boards and ethical guidelines.

Finally, as an essential task, we **plan to conduct an empirical study** focused on writing RRs by individuals engaged in Software Engineering research, such as students and instructors in Empirical Software Engineering courses. Using our proposed template, participants will produce RRs that will then be submitted for peer review. We will analyze reviewer feedback to identify strengths and weaknesses of the template. As part of the study, participants may also be asked to write RRs without the template, enabling a comparative evaluation across dimensions such as completeness, clarity, and methodological rigor. This empirical validation will not only refine our approach but also provide evidence-based recommendations for adopting RRs within the Software Engineering community.

Figure 1 shows a mind map connecting the lessons learned and limitations of our work on RRs with the prospective actions proposed for their improvement. The left side highlights key challenges, such as the need for transparency, accountability, and SE-specific standards. In contrast, the right side presents actions including refining RR types, aligning with publication requirements, OSF customization, metadata development, and conducting empirical studies. The directed edges highlight how each lesson informs a specific action, providing a roadmap that addresses current barriers while promoting reproducibility and rigor in Software Engineering experiments.

Towards an OSF-based Registered Report Template for Software Engineering Controlled Experiments

Fig. 1. Lessons learned and limitations driving prospective actions.

6 FINAL REMARKS

This paper presented a proposal for software engineering controlled experiment registered reports, based on a set of guidelines by Jedlitschka et al. [2008].

We compared all the OSF-registered report types and narrowed them down to four for further analysis. We selected one report type that aligns best with the experiment guidelines. We discussed how the chosen RR type maps to the guidelines. Additionally, we reveal the current limitations in customizing, adding, or creating new RR types under the OSF platform.

We have identified specific actions to write effective RRs for controlled experiments in software engineering. We recognize that establishing guidelines for RRs in software engineering is challenging yet essential, particularly considering the nature of the artifacts in this field.

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